

WORD FORMATION OF PART OF SPEECH NOUN AFFIXATION AND SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

In this given article we analyzed the linguistic features of word formation. There are some similarities and differences between word formation system of Uzbek and English languages. In the article we tried to solve different problems of using affixes and to compare the resemblance and different sides typologically in formation of noun in English and Uzbek languages using the method of affixation. study some ways of word formation and to clarify the theme we presented a lot examples.

Key words: *compound words, classification of compounds, word formation, main ways, conversion, affixation, suffix, prefix, infix, derivative words, components, word stems, abbreviation, acronyms and initialisms.*

It is clear that word-building is one of the main ways of enriching vocabulary. In contrast to word formation, word stems are mainly used as a building material in word addition. As a result of word formation and word attachment, new compound words are formed. They are formed by adding affixes to a whole compound word. Affixation According to Brussmann [2006], affixation is the process of word formation in which stem is expanded by the addition of an affix[p.25]. So, affixation is a morphological process whereby a bound morpheme (an affix) is attached to the base. Moreover, affix is added to the base form or stem of a word in order to modify its meaning or create a

new meaning. Richards and Schmidt [2002] say that affixes are bound to form that can be added: 1) To the beginning of a word (prefix), usually inserted before the word. 2) To end of a word (suffix), usually inserted after the word. 3) Within a word (infix), usually inserted into a word[p.17]. In other words, affixation is divided according to the place they can add to the base. Prefix (affixes that precede the root), example un– as in unhealthy suffix (affixes that follow the root), example ly– as in happily and infix (affixes that are inserted within the root). In contrast, root is the morpheme in which the rest of the word is built. A base is any structure to which affix may be added. While stem is any base to which grammatical affix may be added.

They are formed by adding affixes to a whole compound word. (blue-eyed, dress-maker). But, nevertheless, the process of making such words is done, first of all, by adding cores. (blue + eye = blue-eyed, dress + make = dress-maker). So here the core becomes the main word-forming element of the compound word. There are four **main ways** of word-building in modern English: affixation, composition, conversion abbreviation [8]

Affixation (xushxabar, saylgoh) ,**word-composition** (oqqush, temiryo‘l), **conversion** (kasal, g‘olib), **abbreviation** (O‘zMU) .

Affixation or derivation.

Affixation is one of the most productive ways of word-building throughout the history of English. It consists in adding an affix to the stem of a definite part of speech[2].

Suffixes(-age,-ance,-ant,-ee,-ence,--er/or, -ery,-full,-ion) can change parts of speech as the following:

adjective-to-noun: shortage (‘етишмовчилик, камлик’)

-ness (happy → happiness),

-ness (sad → sadness)

adjective-to-verb: -ize (modern → modernize)

noun-to-adjective: -al (recreation → recreational)

noun-to-verb: -fy (glory → glorify)

verb-to-adjective: -able (wash → washable)

verb-to-noun: -ance (deliver → deliverance)

Prefixation (dis-, anti-,de-,em-,en-,in-,im-, inter-,mid-,non-...) is the formation of words by means of adding a prefix to the stem. In English it is characteristic for forming verbs. Semantic classification of prefixes:

a) prefixes of negative meaning, such as : in- (invaluable), non- (nonferrous)

b) prefixes denoting repetition or reversal actions, such as: de- (decolonize), re- (redo), dis- (discomfort),

c) prefixes denoting time, space, degree relations, such as : inter- (international) , hyper- (hyperactive), ex- (ex-president), pre- (pre-election).

All prefixes were borrowed from other languages in the Uzbek language.

Circumfix (un-imagin-able, un-accept-able,in-advisab-ly,..) is an affix, a morpheme that is placed around another morpheme. Circumfixes contrast with prefixes, attached to the beginning of the words; suffixes, that are attached at the end; and infixes, inserted in the middle.

Infix (-pr-, -mu-, -co-, -os-, -me-, -cir-, -ne-, -fu-, -bac-...) is a word element (a type of affix) that can be inserted within the base form of a word—rather than at its beginning or end—to create a new word or intensify meaning. The process of inserting an infix is called infixation.

¹Webster's New International Dictionary, Second Edition, Springfield, Mass., 1949. P. 98

In some cases, it is more difficult to determine the nature of the construction of compound words. (compare, for example, first nighter - coming to the theater premiere, out-of-towner - living out of town, to weekend - spending the weekend). These help to

conduct word formation analysis. Regardless of their morphological structure, such new structures fall into the category of compound words.

Thus, compounds like *first nighter*, *out-of-towner* are derivative words (first-night + land, out-of-town + land): 1) core + base; 2) core + core + base; 3) stem + stem.

Conversion is a characteristic feature of the English word-building system. It is also called affixless derivation or zero-suffixation [4;99] Conversion refers to the process of changing or converting the class of a word without changing its form.

Examples:

Noun

to verb: bottle (The wine was brewed in France but bottled in Hong Kong.),

Verb to noun: hit (He scored a hit in his first shot.),

Adjective to noun: crazy (Stop shouting and running around like a crazy.),

Adjective to verb: dirty (Don't sit on the floor. You might dirty your dress.)

Conversion is treated differently by different scientists, e.g. prof. A.I. Smirntitsky treats conversion as a morphological way of forming words when one part of speech is formed from another part of speech by changing its paradigm. Conversion is the main way of forming verbs in Modern English [6;58]. Verbs can be formed from nouns of different semantic groups and have different meanings because of that:

a) verbs have instrumental meaning if they are formed from nouns denoting parts of a human body e.g. to eye, to finger, to elbow, to shoulder etc. They have instrumental meaning if they are formed from nouns denoting tools, machines, instruments, weapons, e.g. to hammer, to machine-gun, to rifle.

b) verbs can denote an action characteristic of the living being denoted by the noun from which they have been converted, e.g. to crowd, to wolf.

c) verbs can denote acquisition, addition or deprivation if they are formed from nouns denoting an object, e.g. to fish, to dust, to peel, to paper.

d) verbs can denote an action performed at the place denoted by the noun from which they have been converted, e.g. to park, to garage, to bottle, to corner.

e) verbs can denote an action performed at the time denoted by the noun from which they have been converted e.g. to winter, to week-end

Haspelmath, M. Morphology. London: MacMillan Press LTD.2003
p.56-60

An abbreviation, simply put, is a shortened form of a word. In writing, abbreviations are useful when you need to squeeze a lot of writing into a small space. You can also use them in place of long or cumbersome phrases to make your sentences easier to read. One thing to remember about abbreviations is that certain ones are considered informal. If you are writing something very formal, it's better to err on the side of spelling things out. The other thing to remember is that some readers may not know what an abbreviation means. If the abbreviation is obscure or unfamiliar, make sure to explain what it means the first time you use it.

Acronyms and initialisms. Abbreviations come in a few different varieties. Both acronyms and initialisms are abbreviations that are formed by combining the initial letter or letters of each word into a longer name or phrase. Typically, acronyms and initialisms are written in all capital letters to distinguish them from ordinary words. (When fully spelled out, the words in acronyms and initialisms do not need to be capitalized unless they entail a proper noun.)

An acronym is pronounced as a single word, rather than as a series of letters. *NASA*, for instance, is an acronym. It stands for **N**ational **A**eronautics and **S**pace **A**dministration. Occasionally, an acronym becomes so commonplace that it evolves into an ordinary word that people no longer think of as an acronym. The words *scuba* and *laser*, for instance, originated as acronyms (self contained **u**nderwater **b**reathing **a**pparatus and **l**ight **a**mplification by **s**timulated **e**mission of **r**adiation, respectively).

Initialisms are similar to acronyms in that they are also formed using the first letter of each word in a longer phrase. Unlike acronyms, however, initialisms are pronounced as a series of letters. *NFL* (National Football League), for example, is pronounced *en-*

eff-ell. If you need to use an indefinite article before an acronym or initialism, use the initial *sound* of the word (not necessarily the initial letter) guide your choice. Internet slang often takes the form of initialisms: LOL, IDK, IMO, BRB. Although this type of slang isn't appropriate for important correspondence like emails to your professor or colleagues, or in online comments when you want to be taken seriously, it can be handy for informal online chatting, especially if you type slowly. Abbreviations for courtesy titles and academic degrees. Titles such as *mister*, *miss*, and *doctor*, as well as the names of academic degrees such as *bachelor of arts* and *doctor of philosophy* are almost always abbreviated. In American English, title abbreviations are followed by a period; in British English, the period is omitted.

The most common title abbreviations include:

Mr. = Mister

Mrs. = Mistress (pronounced "missus")

Ms. = (pronounced "miss" or "miz")

Sr. = Senior

Jr. = Junior

Dr. = Doctor

Mr. Green asked Ms. Grey if she had met Dr. Jekyl. (American style)

Mr Green asked Ms Grey if she had met Dr Jekyl. (British style)

The most common academic degree abbreviations include:

B.S. = Bachelor of science

B.A. = Bachelor of Arts

M.A. = Master of Arts

M.B.A. = Master of Business Administration

Ph.D. = Doctor of Philosophy

The periods are optional with abbreviations of academic degrees. Follow whichever style your style guide recommends, or just choose one and use it consistently. When an academic degree is used like a title, it follows a person's name and is set off by commas:

Graphical abbreviations are the result of shortening of words and word-groups only in written speech while orally the corresponding full forms are used. They are used for the economy of space and effort in writing. The oldest group of graphical abbreviations in English is of Latin origin [9].

There are also graphical abbreviations of native origin, where in the spelling we have abbreviations of words and word-groups of the corresponding English equivalents in the full form:

- a) days of the week, e.g. Mon - Monday, Tue - Tuesday etc
- b) names of months, e.g. Apr - April, Aug - August etc.
- c) names of counties in UK, e.g. Yorks - Yorkshire, Berks -Berkshire etc
- d) names of states in USA, e.g. Ala - Alabama, Alas - Alaska etc.
- e) names of address, e.g. Mr., Mrs., Ms., Dr. etc.
- f) military ranks, e.g. capt. -captain, col. - colonel, sgt - sergeant etc.
- g) scientific degrees, e.g. B.A. - Bachelor of Arts, D.M. - Doctor of Medicine .
- h) units of time, length, weight, e.g. f. / ft -foot/feet, sec. - second, in. –inch.

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